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Protector or traitor? -An investigation into the role of M. Perron

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After the battle of Wandiwash, the fragile Indian political scene was left open for any political power to shift the balance of power in their favour and the British East India company did the same and with precision. But even after Wandiwash, some French military adventurers rose to a higher military as well as political status and became the cause of envy and worry for British authorities. The period in which the European Military Adventurers of Hindustan flourished began in 1784, during the Government of Warren Hastings, and ended in 1808 during that of the Marquis Wellesley. Those twenty years saw the rise, the reign, and the ruin of Independent Military Adventure in India. The most famous among them, General Count De Boigne and Perron, were in the service of Maratha chief Sindhia during the last years of eighteenth century. This paper is an attempt to trace the role and impact on M. Perron on Anglo-Maratha relations.

The credit of organising the Maratha units on Europeans lines exclusively goes to Count De Boigne. He drilled the Maratha infantry on French commands and modern European tactics. With the help of this modern army he won many battles for his master Sindhia. To De Boigne belongs the honour of having initiated the wonderful system that took root and grew with the rapidity. He created for Mahadji Sindhia the first complete army of regular troops employed by the Native Princes of the country. The example was soon followed by the Nizam of Hyderabad, and, in a different degree, by Tipu Sultan. He was known for his efficiency and probity as a commander, and was renowned for always paying his troops on time. De Boigne was a brave soldier and good leader but was known for his great organisational abilities. He organised and trained those infantry and artillery brigades which made his master Sindhia the paramount power of his time.

In 1791, Sindhia made him governor of the territory known as the Doab - a small but symbolically important area in north-central India, relatively close to Delhi, which included as the jewel in its crown the historic city of Agra, famous then as now as the home of no less a monument than the Taj Mahal. 1794 witnessed a lively correspondence between de Boigne and John Murray, of the East India Company in Calcutta, concerning the possibilities of restoring

the famous Mughal mausoleum and saving it for posterity.

Sindhia died that same year, and was succeeded by his nephew, a far less forceful individual. Two years later, in 1796, for health reasons but also no doubt sensing that the Maratha star was on the wane, de Boigne decided to leave India for good. He had amassed a huge fortune in Sindhia's service; he had invested part of those monies in the indigo business, acquiring an interest in a European-run concern that specialised in producing the dye for sale in the West. January 1797 saw the adventurer's return to Europe. Owing to the revolutionary instability in France, and given his own royalist and legitimist sympathies, he took up residence in London and later shifted to motherland Chambéry in Savoy. He successfully masterminded the return of his fortune.

Monsieur Perron : Perron (1755-1834), who succeeded De Boigne as commander of European troops under Sindhia was also a French military adventurer, whose name was originally Pierre Cuillier, was born at Luceau in France, the son of a cloth merchant.

In 1780 he went out to India as a sailor on a French frigate deserted on the Malabar Coast, and made his way to upper India, where he enlisted in the Rana of Gohad's corps under a Scotsman named Sangster. In 1790 he took service under De Boigne, and was appointed to the command of his second brigade. He soon got promoted to the rank of second in command under De Boigne. De Boigne explained him "as a man of plain sense, of no talent, but a brave soldier."

In 1795 he assisted to win the battle of Kardla against the nizam of Hyderabad, and on De Boigne's retirement became commander-in-chief of Sindhia's army with all the powers and pomp of his predecessor. His position got even stronger because of long absence of Sindhia from north. He assumed all the powers of administration and ruled the northern plains like a sovereign prince. At the battle of Malpura (1800) he defeated the Rajput forces and received tributes from the chiefs of Jodhpur and Jaipur. He had monopoly over Salt tax and Customs duty. He got the royal privilege of minting coins and his annual salary reached approx £ 16,32, 000.

Perron used his authority visibly without any attempt to hide, and that to over a region which was probably the best in the India. The politically symbolic and strategically important fort of Agra, capital town of Delhi and even The Mughal emperor was under his control as well as the most prosperous region of Doab. He had established various cantonments for twenty thousand soldiers in Doab and built nearly invincible fort at Aligarh.

Lord Wellesley, since his arrival in India in 1798 AD, was suspicious of the possible French attack on India, either by sea or land route. Though today this seems sheer imagination only but contemporaries did not think so. The situation in India was also a catalyst in this scenario. Tipu Sultan of Mysore was trying to secure French military support to drive out English. He had sent ambassadors to Mauritius, the then French colony and even sent an embassy to Paris to meet the directors. Nizam of Hyderabad had raised a trained infantry unit of 14000 men under a French national Monsieur Raymond. Sikh king Ranjeet Singh was also raising army under French commanders and had Perron's influence in Panjab. Holker also had a strong army unit under French commanders. Perron under Sindhia was the most powerful and independent among them all. Wellesley has mentioned in 'Independent State' of Perron.

Wellesley saw all these French units and commanders adverse to the interest of East India Company in India and specially to Perron. "The Moghul has never been an important or dangerous instrument in the hands of the Mahrattas, but the augmentation of M. Perron's influence and power and the growth of a French interest in Hindostan, had given a new aspect to the condition of the Moghul, and that unfortunate Prince might here become a powerful aid to the cause of France in India, under the direction of French agents."

However strong the position of Perron seems, it was evident in the very beginning of the second Maratha war that he did not want to engage in war with company. He was searching for an escape way to Europe along with his accumulated wealth. Governor General had already guessed this situation and on 11 July 1803 wrote to General Lake "It will be highly desirable to detach M. Perron from Sindhia's service by pacific negotiation. M. Perron's inclination certainly is, to dispose of his power to a French purchaser; but I should not be surprised if he were to be found ready to enter into terms with your Excellency, provided he could obtain sufficient security for his personal interests."

Perron, who had for some time been conscious of a decline in Sindhia's favour, started correspondence with General Lake before the commencement of the war.

Perron's Negotiations for Escape Way : General lake started from Kanpur on 7 August 1803. By this

time he was authorised by the Governor General to conclude a convention with Perron, if comes the opportunity, with certain constraints. At the same time Lord Wellesley cautioned Commander-in-Chief Lake to not let M. Perron avail some time or delay the attack in the name of negotiations.

Perron, some time before the opening of the campaign, had addressed himself to the British government to obtain permission to enter the British territories, with the view of executing his intention of withdrawing himself from Daulat Rao Sindhia's service and wanted to avoid the war and safe passage for withdrawal of his property and person. This request was immediately granted by the Governor-general, in a private letter addressed to the commander in chief. But posterior events prevented Perron from profiting by that permission.

On the 20th August the commander in chief received a letter from Perron, wherein he expressed his surprise to see that the British army kept moving, towards Coel wherein Perron fortified himself, and demanded to be informed whether the British government was at war with Sindhia. It indicates, on Perron's side, the intention of bringing about some accommodation, which might prevent an encounter between the British forces and those under Perron's orders. General Lake answered M. Perron by explaining, in a general way, the cause of the approach of his army, and begging him to send a confidential officer with whom he might explain himself on the subject of Perron's letter. Lake flattered himself that Perron would accede to the proposals.

On the 27th August the Lake received another letter from M. Perron, expressing his earnest desire to find some convenient means of avoiding the war, but nevertheless declined the proposition of sending an officer to British under the pretence that such a step would excite the jealousy of the court of Sindhia. Perron, however, demanded a confidential officer to be sent to confer with him. General Lake diplomatically denied the demand. He reasoned that the aim of the conference which he desired with Perron had no reference to the public affairs of the British and Sindhia, but to the private Interests of M. Perron, and to the means of executing, with safe and safety, his design of withdrawing from Sindhia's service. Lake repeated that he was ready to receive an officer from M. Perron, but at the same time told him not to renew his correspondence with M. Perron, unless he was willing to profit by the permission which had been granted, of sending an officer to the British camp; and warned of war if decision delayed.

To buy some more time Perron decided to send his aid-de-camp, Mr. Beckett, to the British camp, to have a further explanation. He answered Lake that it was his intention to stay in Sindhia's service

during the present crisis, and that it was impossible for him to retire until his successor was appointed. Perron by this time had decided to leave Coel, left a strong force there under one of his officers, named Pedron, and marched with his army towards Agra. Coel was stormed on 29 Aug and all the correspondence ended. On the 7th of September, the army marched for Delhi.

However, on the 5th September General Lake received a letter from M. Perron, by which he renewed his demand for leave to retire to Lucknow, across the company's territory. The motive told by Perron for this demand was, that he had just learnt the appointment and approach of his successor, and the treachery of his European officers. The easy capture of a fortress that he and his engineers had rendered, as they believed, impregnable, and the loss of all his military stores, sufficed to show him that he could not hope to withstand the progress of the British; and that it was better for him to resign, at once, than to continue a hopeless struggle, especially as the loss of Aligarh would excite the fury of Sindhia, and possibly lead to his arrest and execution.

Perron, at the same time, requested permission to be escorted to Lucknow by his body guards, and that he might be furnished with an escort of British troops. General Lake granted Perron permission to pass over the company's territory to Lucknow, and authorised the escort of his body guards. The commander in chief required him to begin his march on the second day after receiving the permission, and to prevent his escort from committing any pillage.

Wellesley, from this moment, considered Perron's defection as an event extremely favourable to the success of the British arms, and to the interests of the British government in India. This event relieved the neighbouring states and chiefs from the fear they had of Perron's power. It contributed also to lessen the confidence which the native powers were accustomed to place in the fidelity of their French officers.

Agreeably to the permission of the commander in chief Perron crossed the company's territory and arrived at Lucknow on the 01 October 1803. Special instructions were issued to the resident of Lucknow that Perron should be treated, during his residence at Lucknow, with the distinction due to the rank he held in the service of Doulat Rao Sindhia .

The resident was ordered, in his instructions, to hasten, as much as possible, the departure of M. Perron and his suite from Lucknow. Perron, in

company with Bickett and Fleury, set out from Lucknow to the Bengal presidency, 8th November, accompanied by a European officer and settled the neighbourhood of the French establishment of Chandernagor. Later he shifted to France.

Conclusion : For his desertion to his employer at the time of crisis Perron is much criticised by the scholar. His successor, again a French national, Bourquine was not of that energy, valour and status that he can save a battle against a formidable enemy. With his departure itself, Daulat Rao had lost the war in north. Battle of Laswarre at Delhi between Lake and Bourquin was only an event delay the inevitable. His betrayal left Sindhia no option but to concede a humiliating treaty. Perron abandonment of his master at a critical juncture shook the confidence of Indian princes into their non Indian commanders. This is one of the reasons of why do we not hear of any important non British non Indian commander afterwards.

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